

From Poison to Antidote: Advancing Cybersecurity Education with AI Attack and Defense Training

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Abstract: As artificial intelligence (AI) is being integrated into cybersecurity systems, new risks emerge from adversarial AI threats which target the underlying AI models, such as evasion and poisoning attacks. The direct impact of these attacks is to cause misclassifications thereby undermining their security objectives. Despite the growing importance of these threats, current cybersecurity training exercises do not incorporate adversarial AI scenarios. This paper presents a hands-on training exercise designed to bridge this gap by introducing offensive and defensive tasks involving adversarial AI. Specifically, we construct a training scenario where participants investigate targeted label flipping poisoning attacks on a decision tree classifier trained to detect intrusions in an IoT network. Moreover, the proposed defensive tasks mitigate the impact of these attacks through a simple yet effective fine-tuning of the `class_weight` and `max_depth` hyperparameters. Following the exercise, a questionnaire was given to the participants to evaluate the approach, with the results indicating high levels of understanding, engagement, and interest. Overall, such training exercises not only enhance technical skills and raise awareness of the underlying threats, but also contribute to the development of trustworthy AI systems aligned with the requirements of AI regulatory frameworks such as the EU AI Act.

1 INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming a crucial component of cybersecurity solutions, from automated threat detection to incident response and digital forensics (Jarrett and Choo, 2021). However, cybersecurity training exercises have not been adapted to this change, neglecting to incorporate adversarial and/or robust AI scenarios (Malatji and Tolah, 2024). This gap leaves practitioners unprepared for AI-specific threats, such as evasion attacks, model poisoning, and privacy violations of AI-driven systems. The impact of such adversarial AI attacks can be significant as the performance of the models deteriorates drastically. To address these new threats, cybersecurity training programs must integrate new scenarios that include adversarial and robust AI tasks, thereby preparing practitioners to defend against AI threats appropriately.

Driven by the above motivation, this paper presents a practical cybersecurity training exercise that can bridge the gap between traditional cybersecurity training and adversarial AI threats. Our scenario focuses on both the offensive and defensive aspects of securing AI-based systems. To this purpose, we

design a specific training activity based on the CIC IoT 2023 dataset, in which the participants will apply and study label-flipping poisoning attacks on a decision tree classifier trained to detect intrusions in an IoT network. This setup provides a realistic and high-impact use case, as IoT networks have widespread deployment and decision trees provide an explainable classifier commonly used in lightweight AI deployments. During the exercise, participants observe how varying poisoning rates degrade the performance of the model and gain insight into how easy the AI-based IDS fails its objective under adversarial attacks. On the defensive side, participants apply hyperparameter tuning, adjusting the class weight and the maximum depth of the tree to mitigate the effect of poisoning and restore the model's robustness. For evaluation purposes, the exercise was given to 42 undergraduate students enrolled in a cybersecurity course. Afterwards, the students responded to a set of questions designed to assess comprehension, perceived difficulty, and interest, in order to gather feedback. The results indicate that the exercise was designed to be technically meaningful, helping the participants understand the core ideas and practical workings of adversarial

and robust AI techniques. The main contributions of this paper are described below.

- Design and implementation of a hands-on attack-defense exercise on adversarial AI for IDS.
- Evaluation of the exercise through student feedback, showing that it improves participants' comprehension of adversarial AI concepts.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents how adversarial AI attacks can fool AI driven cybersecurity solutions. Section 3 outlines the scenario description, including details of the utilized dataset and the AI model to attack and defend. Section 4 presents the adversarial and robust AI exercise, analyzing the questions and providing possible solutions. Section 5 presents the questionnaire given to participants who completed the exercise and displays the results. Section 6 discusses limitations and future extensions while Section 7 presents the related work. Finally, 8 concludes the paper.

2 ADVERSARIAL AI AND CYBERSECURITY

Adversarial AI exploits machine learning and deep learning models by designing perturbations to training or testing inputs to fool AI classifiers, downgrading overall performance. The most common methods are evasion attacks (Moskalenko et al., 2023) in which minor changes to features (e.g., pixels in images or bytes in executables) lead to misclassifications at test time. What is more, data poisoning attacks, in which mislabeled or maliciously structured data are secretly injected during training to bias the learned decision boundaries. Label-flipping attacks are a form of data poisoning where the attacker deliberately changes the class labels of selected training samples (e.g., flipping a benign label to malicious or vice versa). This misleads the learning algorithm into constructing erroneous decision boundaries, which in turn degrades the classifier's performance at test time. On the other hand, robust AI is the defensive mechanisms against adversarial attempts. Methods of robust AI include adversarial training, input sanitization and detection of perturbations (Moskalenko et al., 2023).

In cybersecurity, adversarial AI poses serious threats because attackers exploit weaknesses in AI-powered systems to bypass defenses, evade detection, or disrupt operations (Li, 2024). Recent work has also addressed robustness in federated IDS. FedKD-IDS applies knowledge distillation with semi-supervised learning and anti-poisoning aggregation (Quyen et al., 2025), while DPA-FL employs a two-phase filtering

and validation scheme, achieving high resilience even under label-flipping and backdoor attacks (Lai et al., 2023).

3 SCENARIO DESCRIPTION

3.1 Dataset

For the exercise the open source CIC IoT 2023 (Neto et al., 2023; Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity, 2023) dataset is utilized. The initial dataset consists of thirty-four different attacks grouped into eight categories: DDoS, DoS, Mirai, Benign, Spoofing, Recon, Web and Brute Force. Due to the substantial size of the dataset, only a representative subset was retained for the exercise implementation. Moreover, only the DDoS and DoS attack categories were selected for the purposes of this exercise. Afterwards, the DDoS and DoS instances of the same type were merged into one category. For example, the DDoS SYN Flood and the DoS SYN Flood were merged into one category named SYN Flood. After the above-mentioned preprocessing, the final dataset consists of 693,767 rows and 13 classes (see Table 1 for the distribution of each class). With respect to feature selection, the 13 most relevant features from the original set of 39 were retained: "Tot size", "syn_flag_number", "Variance", "TCP", "ICMP", "ack_flag_number", "Header_Length", "psh_flag_number", "IAT", "UDP", "fin_flag_number", "rst_flag_number" and "Std".

Table 1: Class Distribution after Preprocessing.

Class	Number of Samples
Benign	16,568
ACK_FRAGMENTATION	4,303
HTTP_FLOOD	1,529
ICMP_FLOOD	108,660
ICMP_FRAGMENTATION	6,779
MIRAI_FLOOD	39,634
PSHACK_FLOOD	62,167
RSTFIN_FLOOD	61,648
SLOWLORIS	354
SYN_FLOOD	146,815
TCP_FLOOD	108,674
UDP_FLOOD	132,376
UDP_FRAGMENTATION	4,260
Total	693,767

3.2 Model and Evaluation

The AI model selected for the exercise is a decision tree classifier developed in Python 3.13 using the

Scikit-learn library. The train-test split for the evaluation is 80%-20%, respectively. The split is stratified to ensure that both subsets include instances from all classes. The performance metrics are based on accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score. In scikit-learn, the latter three metrics can be averaged in several ways. In this exercise, the *macro-average* option was chosen so that all attack classes were treated equally from the detection model. The decision tree was trained with the default hyperparameter settings of the scikit-learn library. The performance of the decision tree before the poisoning attack was 99.79% accuracy, 95.43% precision, 95.57% recall and 95.49% F1-score. The robustness procedure was based solely on the above-mentioned dataset.

3.3 Scenario and Assumptions

For this exercise, the attack team is going to perform a dataset poisoning attack on the aforementioned IDS dataset using the label flipping technique. For the purposes of the exercise, it is assumed that the participants of the attack team have full access to the model and the dataset (i.e., white-box attack). The attack in this scenario is considered targeted, in the sense that only one specific class will be poisoned. In particular, participants will aim to flip the labels of the ICMP flood class to the benign class. The impact of the attack is that the retrained model with the poisoned dataset will misclassify ICMP flood instances as benign traffic.

Moreover, various poisoning rates will be considered in these exercises ranging from 10% to 50%. The poisoning rate refers to the proportion of training samples that have been maliciously modified or injected by an attacker. Regarding the assessment of the attack's effectiveness, the ASR metric will be utilized, as defined in (1).

$$ASR = \frac{\text{Misclassified Instances on the Test Set}}{\text{Total Number of Instances on the Test Set}} \quad (1)$$

On the other hand, the role of the defensive team is to enhance the robustness of the AI model against poisoning attacks. To this end, two hyperparameters of the model will be adjusted: i) the class weight and ii) the max depth. Using these hyperparameters, the model can reduce its sensitivity to the poisoned samples. This solution, while not generic and therefore not a substitute for established defenses (e.g., robust training, input sanitization), provides a simple workaround that mitigates the impact of data poisoning on decision trees for this specific dataset.

4 ATTACKING AND DEFENDING AN AI-BASED IDS

In this section, we present a series of questions and answers divided into two parts: offensive exercises, which focus on implementing and evaluating poisoning attacks, and defensive exercises, which aim to enhance the robustness of AI models against such attacks. For questions that involve code development, it is assumed that participants may either write the code from scratch, complete partially provided snippets, or take directly the implementation, depending on their level of expertise. The exercise environment is implemented in Google Colab, a free service that requires no setup and provides access to computing resources. The interactive notebook can be accessed at: Google Colab Environment.¹

4.1 Offensive Exercises

Question 1: Run the poisoning attack for different poisoning rates ranging from 0% (clean label) to 50% with step 10 retraining the model to calculate the performance metrics.

Answer: The Python code of *Google Colab Listing 1* implements the attack for different poisoning rates. The code starts by creating a copy of the dataset in order not to modify the original dataset. Then, it retrieves the position indexes of all the ICMP_FLOOD samples in the training dataset. Next, the code randomly selects the specified poisoning rate of ICMP_FLOOD samples and flips their class to Benign. After training the model with the poisoned dataset, the accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score are computed for the different poisoning rates. As mentioned in Section 3.2, the use of the *macro* option for the metrics calculations by considering all classes evenly. The test_encode variable represents the true labels and predictions the predicted ones. Figure 1 shows the confusion matrix for 40% poisoning rate. The final results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Performance Metrics under Different Poisoning Rates.

Poisoning Rate	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
0%	0.9979	0.9543	0.9557	0.9549
10%	0.9874	0.9311	0.9483	0.9374
20%	0.9748	0.9140	0.9405	0.9208
30%	0.9573	0.9034	0.9387	0.9082
40%	0.9348	0.8963	0.9266	0.8916
50%	0.9086	0.8949	0.9183	0.8780

¹https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1R7Qk-mdP10_IhrDIDTlIMYVgVvq-2v9e?usp=sharing

Figure 1: Confusion Matrix for 40% Poisoning Rate.

Question 2: Observe the results of the previous question (see Table 2) and explain why the accuracy is still high even though the poisoning rate is 50%?

Answer: This happens because the ICMP_FLOOD class has 108,660 samples which correspond to approximately 15.66% of the total dataset. Even after 50% of the ICMP_FLOOD training labels are flipped and subsequently misclassified, the model predicts the remaining twelve classes correctly. Their larger share of the remaining samples (84.44%) dominates the metric, so the reported accuracy (and apparent overall performance) stays high (even with *macro* averaged metrics).

Question 3: Run the code below to the ASR for the ICMP flood class for each poisoning rate (from 10% to 50%).

Answer: Based on (1), the ASR value in this case is the ratio of ICMP_FLOOD instances misclassified as Benign to the total number of ICMP_FLOOD instances in the test set. Thus, the ASR is calculated using formula (2).

$$\text{ASR} = \frac{\text{Misclassified ICMP_FLOOD Instances}}{\text{Total ICMP_FLOOD Instances in Test Set}} \quad (2)$$

The code from *Google Colab Listing 2* is used to calculate the ASR. The final results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: ASR for Different Poisoning Rates.

Poisoning Rate	ASR
10%	0.0665
20%	0.1457
30%	0.2588
40%	0.4004
50%	0.5685

4.2 Defensive Exercises

Question 1: Changing which hyperparameters can make the decision tree model more robust to poisoning attacks?

Answer: The relevant hyperparameters are `class_weight` and `max_depth`. Both are set by default to *None* in the Python scikit-learn library. For `class_weight`, in this default state, all classes have weight equal to one and are treated equally during model training. However, if this hyperparameter is set to *balanced*, the classifier automatically adjusts class weights, placing greater emphasis on the minority class. The class weight w_i is calculated using the formula (3).

$$w_i = \frac{N}{K \cdot n_i}, \quad (3)$$

where N is the total number of training samples, K is the number of distinct classes, and n_i is the number of samples belonging to class i .

Therefore, when labels are flipped during the poisoning attack, a class imbalance arises because only instances of the ICMP_FLOOD class are changed to Benign, but not the reverse. Thus, by changing the `class_weight` parameter to *balanced*, the model assigns increased importance to the remaining minority class (i.e., ICMP_FLOOD) instances. Since the minority class consists of ICMP_FLOOD instances whose labels were not flipped, the model amplifies the weight of the few correct ICMP_FLOOD instances left. As a result, the decision tree is built in a way that classifies instances that have characteristics of the ICMP_FLOOD class as ICMP_FLOOD despite being labeled as Benign.

Note also that as the poisoning rate increases, the size of the minority class decreases, thereby further increasing its associated weight. Consequently, increasing the poisoning rate will not significantly degrade the model's ability to correctly classify the ICMP_FLOOD instances. However, at extreme poisoning rates (e.g., $> 50\%$), the `class_weight` parameter will not be able to cope with the diminished minority class and the model will be affected.

On the other hand, `max_depth` leverages the maximum depth that the tree will reach. By these means, if the hyperparameter is set to 20, the path from the root to the deepest leaf can go through 20 nodes (including the root). By default, no restrictions are applied to the depth of the tree, allowing it to grow as deep as necessary. Each new sample entering the tree initially has maximum entropy or Gini impurity (depending on the tree), which decreases as the sample goes deeper into the tree until reaching the lowest point and thus making the final decision. This condition determines the tree depth if the hyperparameter

isn't set to any specific number. It is important to note that every new sample is assigned a class when entering the tree, which can be changed multiple times as it goes deeper until the final decision is reached. By setting a limit to the depth of the tree, we prevent unnecessary computational overhead and excessive calculations that could ultimately cause confusion in the decision-making process and therefore false predictions.

Question 2: Retrain in order to evaluate the performance of the model.

Answer: The same code from section 4.1 (*Google Colab Listing 1*) can be utilized with the only modification of the hyperparameter `class_weight` to *balanced* when initializing the classifier and `max_depth` to 20 (see *Google Colab Listing 3*). The final results are shown in Table 4. Figure 2 illustrates the confusion matrix for 40% poisoning after parameter tuning.

Figure 2: Confusion Matrix for 40% Poisoning Rate after parameter tuning.

Question 3: Recalculate the ASR values to validate the robustness of the model.

Answer: The code from *Google Colab Listing 2* can be employed (see *Google Colab Listing 4*), and the results presented in the last column of Table 4 indicate that ASR values remain low even at 50% poisoning rate.

Table 4: Performance metrics and ASR value after setting `class_weight` to *balanced* and `max_depth` to 20.

Poisoning Rate	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	ASR
0%	0.9978	0.9437	0.9600	0.9499	0.0000
10%	0.9970	0.9404	0.9492	0.9434	0.0037
20%	0.9966	0.9457	0.9530	0.9484	0.0069
30%	0.9954	0.9428	0.9520	0.9464	0.0146
40%	0.9917	0.9284	0.9572	0.9394	0.0382
50%	0.9932	0.9283	0.9535	0.9384	0.0273

Note that while this fine-tuning makes the model robust to the attack, a slight reduction in performance can be observed.

5 EVALUATION

To evaluate our approach, we designed a feedback questionnaire that participants can complete after the exercise. The questionnaire was designed based on well-established dimensions of course engagement reported in the literature (Mandernach et al., 2011). All questions have a restricted number of answers measured on a Likert scale of **1** (very low) – **5** (very high). The participants were final-year university students who attended the computer security class and had basic AI knowledge without familiarity with adversarial AI concepts. Below is the questionnaire and the responses given by the 42 students who participated in the exercise.

Table 5: Evaluation questionnaire.

Questions	
Q1	How well did you understand what a label flipping attack is?
Q2	In what scale do you feel you could explain this attack to someone else using your own words?
Q3	In what scale did you understand the reasoning behind why parameter tuning improves the model's robustness?
Q4	How clear were the questions in the exercise in guiding you through the task?
Q5	How would you rate the overall difficulty for your level?
Q6	How interested are you in trying this attack on another model (e.g., logistic regression or neural network)?
Q7	How interested are you in seeing different type of adversarial attack next time?
Q8	How interested are you in seeing the same attack in a different domain (e.g., malware)?
Q9	How interested are you in exploring more defense strategies beyond parameter tuning?

The feedback was predominantly positive. In detail, about **Q1**, the largest group (57.2% collectively) selected rating 5 (42.9%) or 4 (14.3%) on the Likert scale, indicating that nearly half of the participants felt they understood label flipping attacks very well. A moderate understanding is reflected by those selecting rating 3 (21.4%). A notable minority (21.4%) reported very low understanding selecting rating 1, while no one selected rating 2. **Q2** shows that half of the students (50% combined) selected rating 5 (28.6%) or 4 (21.4%), indicating a high level of confidence in explaining the label flipping attack to others. Nearly one fifth selected 3 (21.4%), suggesting moderate explanatory confidence. However, 28.5% reported low confidence (rating 1 (21.4%) and 2 (7.1%)). For **Q3** a clear majority (64.3%) selected 5 (28.6%) or 4 (35.7%), indicating a good to very strong understanding of why the model is robust after the changes. Nearly one sixth of students selected rating 3 (14.3%), which reflects partial or surface-level understanding, while 21.4% of the students reported low understanding (rating 1 - 14.3% and 2 - 7.1%),

indicating that a smaller but non-negligible group did not fully grasp the robustness explanation.

For **Q4**, more than half of the participants (57.1%) selected rating 5, while an additional 21.4% selected 4 (78.5% total). This means that nearly four out of five respondents felt that the questions were clear or very clear. Only a small minority expressed moderate clarity (14.3%), and almost no respondents reported low clarity, with no selections for rating 1 and only 7.2% for 2. Overall, this distribution suggests that the wording and structure of the exercise questions were effective and did not pose a significant barrier to understanding. **Q5** results suggest that most of the students (35.7%) rated the difficulty as low (rating 2), followed by a notable group (28.6%) indicating high difficulty (rating 4). Additionally, 21.4% rated the exercise as very easy (rating 1), while very few respondents (7.1% for each) selected the midpoint rating 3 or the highest difficulty rating 5. This pattern suggests that the exercise was generally perceived as accessible, though not uniformly easy, and that it appropriately challenged a subset of participants without being overwhelmingly difficult for most.

The responses to **Q6–Q9** indicate a consistently high level of interest in further exploration of adversarial AI topics. For **Q6**, a strong majority of participants (71.4%) reported very high interest (rating 5) in testing the same attack on a different machine learning model, with an additional 21.4% selecting rating 4 and only 7.1% rating 3. Similarly, **Q7** shows even stronger enthusiasm for exploring a different type of attack in the future, with 78.6% selecting 5, 14.3% rating 4 and again 7.1% rating 3. The interest also remained high in applying the same label flipping attack to a different cybersecurity domain for **Q8**, where 64.3% selected rating 5 and 35.7% rating 4, with no neutral or negative responses. Finally, **Q9** demonstrates a clear willingness to explore additional defense strategies beyond hyperparameter tuning, exhibiting the same response pattern as **Q7**. Overall, across all four questions (i.e., **Q6–Q9**), more than 85% of responses consistently fall in the upper end of the scale, indicating a high level of interest in deeper and broader exploration of the topic.

6 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE EXTENSIONS

The proposed exercise lacks elements of gamification, such as a scoring system that would foster competition and motivation. It is also not interactive in the sense that participants do not engage in real-time activities, which makes the experience less dy-

namic. Traditional cybersecurity exercises have established various forms of practical training, including Jeopardy-style CTFs, Attack-defense (sometimes called “red vs blue”), and King-of-the-Hill. What is more, there is active research on how to improve various aspects of cybersecurity training such as pointing systems, gamification elements, virtualization technologies (Cole, 2022; Érsok et al., 2024). However, designing an interactive, CTF-like training exercise for AI driven cybersecurity solutions, and more generally for AI systems, presents some technical challenges. In our particular case of adversarial and robust AI exercises, it is not straightforward how to define a “winner” among participants. Fooling an AI model with adversarial AI or improving the robustness of a model may be achieved in multiple ways, making it difficult to assess the effectiveness of the submissions. Besides, some scenarios such as adversarial learning for robustness require (re)training an AI model, a computationally intensive task that demands appropriate infrastructure. In this case, large neural networks with millions of parameters may require significant time to train, which would limit the feasibility of a real-time competition. Finally, another hurdle is related to the fact that it is not clear whether cybersecurity professionals have the necessary knowledge to engage with adversarial and robust AI challenges, which is a demanding field of expertise outside cybersecurity.

To overcome these challenges, a well-structured AI-based cybersecurity training exercise must make several design trade-offs. First, small models and subsets of datasets should be utilized for efficiency. Hardware and cost issues should also be considered. Moreover, weighted scores should be introduced to assess the overall performance of a model, taking into account various parameters of the model, such as perturbation rate, robust model accuracy, attack success rate, etc.

As future work, we plan to introduce more interactive steps that will incorporate traditional cybersecurity tasks alongside adversarial AI components. Specifically, participants in the attacker role will be required to execute attacks such as DoS using standard tools (e.g., `hping3` or `scapy`). By capturing the network traffic in real-time, a dedicated parser will automatically extract relevant features from the `.pcap` file (e.g., packet rates, flags, flow statistics), which will serve as input to the AI model under test. This requires the deployment of the AI model in a virtual environment (e.g., a docker), which serves as the runtime context for the model during the exercise.

7 RELATED WORK

Although there is a vast body of research combining AI with cybersecurity, very few works focus on enhancing the educational landscape at the intersection of these two fields. The closest work to ours is Maestro (Geleta et al., 2023), a gamified educational platform designed to teach robust AI concepts through interactive and competitive programming tasks. The platform emphasizes hands-on learning by engaging students in three phases: the Attack Phase, where students design adversarial attacks to exploit vulnerabilities in AI models; the Defense Phase, where they develop strategies to defend against such attacks; and the War Phase, which pits offensive and defensive techniques against each other in a competitive environment. Students also have access to the Maestro leaderboard, where their scores, ranks and/or possible errors are displayed, providing feedback on their submitted solutions. Maestro evaluates each submission with metrics for efficiency (i.e., runtime overhead, resource consumption) and effectiveness (stealthiness of an adversarial attack, prediction accuracy). The authors also mention that a weighted sum is used for the overall score without providing further details. Based on an evaluation carried out at the University of California, Irvine (UCI), the obtained results suggest that Maestro has successfully gamified the learning environment driving students to interaction, mastery of robust AI concepts and increased learner autonomy.

Towards this direction, AdvEx (You et al., 2025) is a multi-level interactive visualization system that comprehensively presents the properties and impacts of evasion attacks on different image classifiers for novice adversarial AI learners. The quantitative and qualitative assessment of AdvEx with user studies and expert interviews showed the proposed learning system is not only highly effective as a visualization tool for understanding adversarial AI mechanisms but also provides an engaging and enjoyable learning experience, thus demonstrating its overall benefits for learners.

The authors of (Mayoral-Vilches et al., 2025) introduced CAI Fluency, an educational platform of the Cybersecurity AI (CAI) framework dedicated to democratizing the knowledge and application of cybersecurity AI tools in the global security community. The framework emphasizes that training is essential to bridge the significant skill gap inherent in using complex Generative and Agentic AI, as proficiency requires understanding both cybersecurity principles and AI concepts. Furthermore, the platform aims to instill the critical thinking and ethical awareness needed for responsible AI use in security contexts.

Ashktorab et al. (Ashktorab et al., 2021) presented an interesting approach that gamifies backdoor attack detection and learning. The game allows users to explore visual clusters of training data, identify poisoned samples, and guess the backdoor trigger by submitting test images, all while using gamified elements like blur levels and limited "peeks" to enhance engagement. It should be noted that the researchers evaluated the game with semi-structured interviews and a Mechanical Turk deployment with sixty-eight users. Users showed creativity in fooling the model and the game successfully crowdsourced diverse data, including new potential backdoor triggers while participants were also motivated to learn about backdoor poisoning.

Another work (Grover et al., 2023) presents an initiative called ACT (AI & Cybersecurity for Teens), which aims to integrate AI and machine learning topics into high school cybersecurity curricula. The goal was to make AI concepts such as decision trees, adversarial thinking, accessible to teens by embedding them in realistic cybersecurity scenarios like bot detection, phishing, cyberbullying, and denial-of-service attacks. Through workshops with high school teachers, the authors found that ACT effectively increased teacher confidence and interest in teaching AI within cybersecurity contexts, although some activities (e.g., GANs) were seen as too advanced for introductory courses. In essence, our work extends (Grover et al., 2023) by advocating training exercises for adversarial and robust AI at the university level rather than in high school due to the complexity of the topics.

Finally, beyond research works, educational platforms are emerging that provide a playground for adversarial AI. For example, AIGoat² is an open-source project that provides a deliberately vulnerable AI infrastructure to simulate the OWASP Machine Learning Security Top 10 risks³. Commercial platforms are also actively being developed to offer offensive AI challenges⁴.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces a training scenario to fill the gap between conventional cybersecurity training exercises and the emerging challenges of adversarial AI. The training scenario focused on attacking and defending an AI model for IDS. Based on the CIC IoT 2023

²<https://github.com/orcasecurity-research/AIGoat>

³<https://owasp.org/www-project-machine-learning-security-top-10/>

⁴<https://dreadnode.io/crucible>

dataset, practical tasks were developed in which the offensive team applied targeted label-flipping attacks on a decision tree classifier and systematically studied how the performance of the model is affected by different poisoning rates. Defensive measures were applied to counteract such attacks by carefully modifying model hyperparameters, namely `class_weight` and `max_depth`, to make the classifier more robust with minimal degradation in performance. Overall, we argue that integrating adversarial AI into cybersecurity training and education is essential for developing skills in threat mitigation and supporting the creation of resilient AI systems in accordance with emerging regulations such as the AI Act.

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